

Smarter Use of Digital Technologies in Schools: Lessons from European Evidence on ICT and School Efficiency

Tommaso Agasisti¹ & Mara Soncin¹

1. Politecnico di Milano

Summary

1. Evidence from more than 5,300 schools across 21 European countries shows that schools become more efficient when digital technologies are integrated into teaching in meaningful ways, not simply when more devices are available.
2. The most effective digital practices are those that actively engage students in research, problem-solving, data analysis, collaboration, and project-based learning.
3. Moderate and purposeful use of ICT appears more beneficial than excessive use. More screen time alone does not automatically improve educational outcomes.
4. Policies should move beyond infrastructure investment and focus more strongly on teacher training, digital pedagogy, and balanced integration of technology into classroom activities.

1. Introduction

Digital technologies are now deeply embedded in educational systems across Europe. Governments and schools have invested heavily in devices, internet connectivity, online learning platforms, and digital teaching tools, especially after the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the importance of technology for ensuring continuity of learning.

At the European level, initiatives such as the European Commission's Digital Education Action Plan and the DigCompEdu framework have emphasized the strategic importance of digital competencies for both students and

teachers. At the same time, the rapid diffusion of Artificial Intelligence tools in education has intensified the debate about how technology should be used in schools.

Despite these investments, an important question remains open: does technology actually help schools achieve better educational results?

Previous research has often produced mixed findings. Simply providing schools with more digital devices does not always lead to better student performance. Increasingly, evidence suggests that the educational value of ICT depends more on how technology is used than on its mere availability.

This policy brief summarizes evidence from a recent study examining how ICT affects school efficiency across European countries. School efficiency refers to the ability of schools to achieve strong educational outcomes while making effective use of available resources.

2. Background, Data and Methods

The study uses data from the OECD PISA 2022 survey and includes 5,360 schools from 21 European Union countries. The analysis examines how schools transform educational resources into student learning outcomes in mathematics, reading, and science.

The study considers both (i) school resources and contextual conditions (such as socio-economic background, educational resources, and teacher-student ratios), and (ii) ICT-related factors, including digital infrastructure, frequency of technology use, and the types of digital learning activities carried out in classrooms.

Four broad ICT dimensions were analyzed:

1. **Digital access and infrastructure:** Availability of devices, internet quality, technical support, and teacher digital readiness.
2. **General ICT use:** Frequency of use of laptops, online platforms, educational software, and other digital tools.
3. **ICT integration into teaching subjects:** Use of digital tools in mathematics, reading, science, and computer science lessons.
4. **Digital learning activities:** Student activities such as online research, data analysis, collaborative digital projects, and educational games.

The research combines advanced efficiency analysis with machine learning techniques in order to identify which ICT practices are most strongly associated with better school performance..

3. Main Findings from the Empirical Analysis

The empirical analysis shows that ICT plays an important role in shaping school efficiency across European countries. Schools tend to achieve better educational outcomes when digital technologies are meaningfully integrated into teaching and learning activities, rather than simply being available as infrastructure or equipment. In other words, the educational value of ICT depends less on the number of devices present in schools and more on how these technologies are actually used in classroom practices.

The findings reveal that the most effective forms of ICT use are those that actively engage students in learning processes. Schools where students frequently conduct independent online research, analyze and interpret data, work on real-world problems, collaborate on digital projects, create digital content, and use educational games in structured ways tend to display higher levels of efficiency. These activities appear to strengthen critical thinking, autonomy, creativity, and active participation, allowing schools to obtain stronger educational outcomes from the resources available to them.

At the same time, the study highlights that the relationship between ICT and school efficiency is not linear. The results support a “moderation effect,” showing that schools perform better when technology is used in balanced and purposeful ways. Occasional but well-designed integration of ICT into

classroom activities is associated with better outcomes than very intensive or continuous digital exposure, which may instead contribute to distraction, cognitive overload, or screen fatigue.

The analysis also points to important differences across European education systems. Nordic countries generally show stronger integration of digital tools into teaching practices, while other countries display weaker connections between technological infrastructure and classroom use. These differences suggest that national context, teacher preparation, school leadership, and broader educational policies all play a crucial role in determining whether investments in digital technologies effectively contribute to improving school performance.

4. Policy and Managerial Implications

The findings of this study suggest that educational policies should move beyond a narrow focus on technological infrastructure alone. While providing schools with digital devices, reliable internet access, and technical resources remains essential, these investments are unlikely to generate meaningful improvements unless they are accompanied by strategies that support the pedagogical integration of technology into teaching and learning processes. Simply increasing access to ICT does not automatically translate into better educational outcomes.

A central implication concerns the role of teachers. The effective use of ICT depends heavily on teachers' capacity to integrate digital tools into classroom activities in ways that promote student engagement and deeper learning. For this reason, professional

development initiatives should not be limited to technical training. Instead, they should also strengthen teachers' competencies in digital pedagogy, project-based learning, classroom integration strategies, and the critical and responsible use of technology. Equally important is helping teachers develop balanced approaches that combine digital and non-digital teaching methods according to educational needs.

The results also indicate that schools should avoid equating "more technology" with "better education." Digital tools appear most effective when they are used selectively, purposefully, and in alignment with learning objectives. Educational policies should therefore encourage forms of ICT use that promote collaboration, critical thinking, problem-solving, and active student participation, while also paying attention to the risks associated with excessive screen exposure and continuous digital stimulation.

School leadership emerges as another crucial factor in successful digital transformation. Principals and school management teams play an important role in shaping the culture surrounding technology use within schools. Effective implementation of ICT requires a clear educational vision, coordination among teachers, monitoring of digital practices, and opportunities for sharing successful experiences and innovative approaches across the school community. In this sense, digital transformation should be understood not only as a technological process, but also as an organizational and cultural change.

Finally, the rapid diffusion of Generative Artificial Intelligence tools in education makes digital literacy and pedagogical guidance even more important. Schools will increasingly need policies capable of ensuring that AI technologies support learning while

preserving human interaction, ethical awareness, critical thinking, and students' capacity for independent reasoning. Preparing education systems for the AI era therefore requires not only technological readiness, but also strong pedagogical and managerial leadership.

What is EFFEct ?

EFFEct is an impact-driven research project aiming to enhance the quality of education in the EU by providing evidence-based policy recommendations and conducting rigorous research on the education policies of individual EU member states.

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